

Seasonal abundance of shorebirds at Aracaju, Sergipe, Brazil

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Shorebirds were counted weekly between Jan 2003 and Apr 2005 along 1.7 km of a 200 m wide mangrove-lined creek at Aracaju, Sergipe State, NE Brazil. 19 shorebird species were recorded of which 17 were Nearctic migrants. By far the most abundant species was Semipalmated Plover, accounting for more than half the aggregate total. Largest numbers of most migrants were observed during southward migration in Oct and Nov and the largest single day count of all species was of 4,046 on 11 Oct 2004. Eight Nearctic species were recorded during both June and July, their breeding season, indicating the presence of non-breeding immatures. This study highlights the importance for migrant shorebirds of this little-studied part of the South American coast and discusses the conservation problems they face.

INTRODUCTION

Nearctic shorebirds that migrate to South America reach their wintering sites by several routes (Morrison 1984, Myers *et al.* 1990). Several species migrate long distances, up to 12,000 km, between their arctic or sub-arctic breeding grounds and their wintering areas in South America. These journeys require several refuelling stops (Skagen & Knopf 1994). Coastal migrants are renowned for long flights over extensive bodies of water that are preceded by long refuelling stops (Gratto-Trevor 1992). These stop-over sites often provide a unique combination of food resources and habitat necessary to support a large number of shorebirds (Myers *et al.* 1979). Examples of important sites in Brazil are the Maranhão Coast and Lagoa do Peixe. Such stopover sites are important because a large proportion of a species' population may be concentrated at these few sites during migration. The Sergipe coast is an important site for shorebirds from Sep to May.

The migratory routes of birds are best known because of their diurnal habits and large, often conspicuous numbers (Orr 1986). In the Americas, the large number of migrant birds of many species that leave their northern breeding grounds to spend the austral summer in South America is especially noteworthy (Sick 1997). Although sandy beaches occur along most of the Atlantic coast of tropical and subtropical America and many species of Neotropical birds are known to live in or use this habitat (Sick 1997), most of the information concerning this avifauna comes from the northern Neotropics or southern North America (Barbieri & Pinna 2007, Olmos & Silva 2001, Vooren & Brusque 1999). There is little information on the avifauna of the tropical and subtropical coast of eastern Brazil. Moreover there are few checklists and or studies of birds using mangroves along that coast (Barbieri & Mendonça 2005, Vooren & Chiaradia 1990).

Most New World shorebirds nest on dry Arctic tundra (Cramp & Simmons 1983, Manning & Macpherson 1961, Myers *et al.* 1990,). Shorebirds migrate along the American coasts to wintering areas such as Lagoa do Peixe ("Fish

Lagoon") in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil, Tierra del Fuego, Argentina, and the coasts of Peru and Chile (Myers *et al.* 1990). These species migrate long distances and are specialized in habitat and prey, and concentrate on sandy beaches, marshes and mangroves (Burger & Gochfeld 1991). Although the diets of shorebirds may be catholic, different species take different sized prey and may also display some habitat segregation (Brown & McLachlan 1990).

The route followed by many of these species during their northward migration (Mar–Apr) is through the Amazon region of South America then to the southeast coast of the United States. During their southward migration (Sep–Oct), birds leave breeding areas to feed at stopover sites along both coasts of the United States, the Caribbean, northern Brazil and then through Amazonia, to Lagoa do Peixe and beyond (Myers *et al.* 1990).

During migration, these birds depend, on marine coastal habitats, mainly sandy beaches (Myers *et al.* 1979) and mangrove areas. There are no published quantitative studies of migrant shorebird populations from the Sergipe coast of NE Brazil. Insufficient information exists with respect to the migration routes or stopover sites used by shorebirds. The Sergipe coast is of great importance for shorebirds from Sep to May. The present paper documents the seasonal abundance and distribution of shorebirds at Aracaju on the coast of Sergipe and shows the importance of this area as a migration route and feeding ground.

METHODS AND STUDY AREA

Much of the coast of Sergipe (163 km) is comprised of sandy sediments. There are five estuaries, as well as swamps, dunes, restingas, forests and mangroves. These ecosystems support a resident and migratory avifauna from both North and South Hemispheres and include several vulnerable species. The tidal range is small (about 2.5 m) and winds often exert an overriding influence on sea level, which is lower during the prevailing northeasterlies, and higher when the wind is southerly. Most beaches have a gentle slope (4–6°)

so intertidal areas are wide (around 250 m) and support high densities of invertebrates.

On average, shorebird censuses were carried out every nine days between 4 Jan 2003 and 8 Apr 2005 along a 1.7 km stretch of mangrove-lined creek near Aracaju City, Sergipe State, NE Brazil (Fig. 1). Birds were counted while the observer walked northward along the lower beach and covered an area 1.7 km × 200 m (0.34 km²) following the methodology of Barbieri & Pinna (2007) and Bibby *et al.* (1992). Censuses were made between 07.00 and 11.30 h during the lowest part of the tidal cycle. Birds were identified and counted using 7 × 50 and 20 × 60 binoculars. In all, 92 censuses were made, each lasting 2.5 to 4.0 h. The number of censuses in each month of the year ranged from five in Nov to ten in Apr and averaged 7.7 (Table 1). The study site is one of several similar sites along the coast of Sergipe. Therefore the results represent a sample of what occurs and it is likely that much greater numbers would be recorded in a more wide ranging census.

RESULTS

Altogether 19 species were recorded; all but three were long-distance Nearctic migrants (Collared Plover and Southern Lapwing, which are endemic to South America, and Wilson's Plover, which breeds in the northern tropics and is a migrant to Brazil). When all 92 counts are aggregated to give a measure of relative abundance, by far the most numerous species was Semipalmated Plover, which comprised more than half the total. Seven other species exceeded 1% (Semipalmated Sandpiper, Least Sandpiper, Ruddy Turnstone, Sanderling, Black-bellied Plover, Whimbrel and White-rumped Sandpiper; Table 2). Together, these eight species made up 97% of the aggregate total, but eleven more species were recorded in relatively small numbers.

Eight species were recorded in all months of the year, and eight more in at least nine months; American Golden Plovers were only recorded in seven months and Red Knots in six months (Table 3). Wilson's Plovers were only recorded in three counts between 6 Nov and 5 Dec 2003, just two individuals on each occasion, probably the same birds.

As a means of comparing abundance patterns between species Table 3 presents an "evenness index" (E) for each species:

$$E = 1 / \sum(p_i)^2$$

where p_i is the mean count for the i -th month expressed as a proportion of the aggregate count for all 12 months.

This index encapsulates the degree to which each species' occurrence is restricted to the fewest months (low evenness) or spread evenly across the most months (high evenness). Therefore species that occur in relatively few months and/or whose numbers show large variation between months have low evenness scores (e.g. Greater Yellowlegs, American Golden Plover, Red Knot and Hudsonian Godwit); whereas those that occur in significant numbers fairly evenly throughout the year have high evenness scores (e.g. Whimbrel, Sanderling, Least Sandpiper and Ruddy Turnstone). As would be

Fig. 1. Location of study site: part of a mangrove-lined creek flowing into the Rio Sergipe Estuary, Aracaju, Sergipe State, Brazil.

expected, the two South American endemics, Collared Plover and Southern Lapwing, both have high scores, though they are not the highest.

Table 3 also shows correlation coefficients for each species between the mean monthly counts and the proportion of counts in each month that the species was recorded. These indicate that for most species with low evenness scores there is a highly significant correlation between presence/absence and abundance. Therefore for such species merely recording presence/absence several times a month will give a good indication of monthly numerical variation.

The majority of Nearctic migrants were most abundant during southward migration in Sep–Dec (the maximum shorebirds recorded in a single day was 4,036 on 11 Oct 2004), less abundant during Jan–Apr and least abundant or absent during May–Aug (see the Appendix). Only Short-billed Dowitchers, Hudsonian Godwits, Willets, Spotted Sandpipers, Red Knots and Least Sandpipers were more abundant during northward migration.

Small numbers of eight Nearctic migrants were recorded in both June and July indicating that a part of their populations remain in the Southern Hemisphere during the breeding season. Many of the Semipalmated Plovers seen in June and July had less-developed breeding plumage compared with the adults, indicating that they were one-year-olds. Both yellowleg species were recorded in July but not June, but six species were not recorded in either month (American Golden Plover, Hudsonian Godwit, Spotted Sandpiper, Red Knot, Semipalmated Sandpiper, and White-rumped Sandpiper).

DISCUSSION

There is plenty of evidence that large numbers of shorebirds are to be found along the Atlantic coast of southern Brazil from September to November (Barbieri & Mendonça 2005, Branco 2003, Harrington *et al.* 1986, Vooren & Chiaradia 1990) and in the interior of Venezuela (Thomas 1987), but there have been very few studies of shorebirds in the State

Table 1. Number of shorebird counts conducted in each month at Aracaju, NE Brazil, between 4 Jan 2003 and 8 Apr 2005

Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
6	9	8	10	8	8	7	7	9	8	5	7

Table 2. Aggregate numbers of shorebirds in 92 counts between Jan 2003 and Apr 2005 at Aracaju, Sergipe, Brazil, ordered according to abundance

Species	Aggregate of counts	%
Semipalmated Plover <i>Charadrius semipalmatus</i>	58,014	58.78
Semipalmated Sandpiper <i>Calidris pusilla</i>	12,446	12.61
Least Sandpiper <i>Calidris minutilla</i>	10,474	10.61
Ruddy Turnstone <i>Arenaria interpres</i>	5,057	5.12
Sanderling <i>Calidris alba</i>	4,872	4.94
Black-bellied Plover <i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	1,906	1.93
Whimbrel <i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	1,584	1.60
White-rumped Sandpiper <i>Calidris fuscicollis</i>	1,436	1.46
Short-billed Dowitcher <i>Limnodromus griseus</i>	694	0.70
Red Knot <i>Calidris canutus</i>	516	0.52
Greater Yellowlegs <i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	365	0.37
Willet <i>Catoptrophorus semipalmatus</i>	309	0.31
Lesser Yellowlegs <i>Tringa flavipes</i>	246	0.25
Southern Lapwing <i>Vanellus chilensis</i>	209	0.21
Spotted Sandpiper <i>Actitis macularia</i>	158	0.16
American Golden Plover <i>Pluvialis dominica</i>	155	0.16
Hudsonian Godwit <i>Limosa haemastica</i>	145	0.15
Collared Plover <i>Charadrius collaris</i>	102	0.10
Wilson's Plover <i>Charadrius wilsonia</i>	6	0.01
Total	98,694	100

of Sergipe (Almeida & Barbieri 2005). The Aracaju counts demonstrate that this area is also an important stopover site for many Nearctic migrants and is one of the best places to study shorebirds in NE Brazil.

In their evaluation of Sanderling migration routes, Myers *et al.* (1990) suggest that the main route through Brazil is between the coast of Maranhão in the north and Lagoa do Peixe, Rio Grande do Sul, in the south. Similarly, Niles *et al.* (2007) suggest that Red Knots fly overland between these

areas, bypassing the NE coast. However, the Aracaju counts show that considerable numbers of many shorebird species, including Sanderlings and Red Knots, take this route. This is consistent with Sick's (1997) statement that shorebirds are frequently found along the whole Brazilian coast.

The great variation in the Aracaju counts both within and between months indicates that most birds are passage migrants moving north or south along the Sergipe coast, as was also noted for gulls (*Lari*) and sandpipers (*Scolopacidae*) by Barrames & Pereira (1992). In this study, the weekly counts may have missed some peak numbers. However, it is likely that most shorebirds remain in the area for at least a week in order to build up adequate fat reserves for onward migration. Therefore the counts should reflect migration phenology fairly accurately (Barbieri & Mendonça 2005).

The presence of small numbers of Red Knots in the study area, a narrow, mangrove-lined creek, is surprising because knots often appear to avoid such confined areas; probably because of the increased risk of predation (Niles *et al.* 2007). This may be an indication of good food resources in the study area and/or the amount of disturbance affecting other potential habitat nearby.

In most of the arctic- and subarctic-breeding shorebirds that migrate to the Southern Hemisphere, the juveniles stay behind and do not migrate to the breeding grounds until they are two or three years old, though there are exceptions, for example most Little Stints *Calidris minuta* from Africa and Sharp-tailed Sandpipers *Calidris acuminata* from Australia migrate north in their first year (Barbieri & Mendonça 2005, Belton 1984, Higgins & Davies 1996, Urban *et al.* 1986, Vooren & Chiaradia 1990). The Aracaju counts show that small numbers of eight northern-breeding shorebirds remain in NE Brazil during the nesting season: Black-bellied Plover, Semipalmated Plover, Short-billed Dowitcher, Whimbrel, Willet, Ruddy Turnstone, Sanderling and Least Sandpiper.

Table 3. Statistics of monthly shorebird counts at Aracaju, Sergipe, Brazil, between Jan 2003 and Apr 2005. Column 2: number of months of the year in which the species was recorded at least once; Column 3: Evenness Index (see text); Columns 4–6: Spearman rank correlation coefficients (R_s) between the mean monthly counts and the proportion of counts in which the species was recorded. In view of the repeated correlations (17), it is appropriate to apply the Bonferroni correction and only accept significance when $p < (0.05/17) = 0.003$. Note that as Semipalmated Plovers were recorded in all counts, there can be no correlation. Species are ordered by increasing values of the Evenness Index.

	No. of months of year species recorded	Evenness index	Correlation for each month of mean count and proportion of counts when species present		
			R_s	p-value	Significance
Greater Yellowlegs	9	3.18	0.894	<0.001	*
American Golden Plover	7	3.95	0.992	<0.001	*
Red Knot	6	4.24	0.974	<0.001	*
Hudsonian Godwit	10	5.38	0.926	<0.001	*
White-rumped Sandpiper	9	5.51	0.979	<0.001	*
Lesser Yellowlegs	11	6.34	0.856	<0.001	*
Semipalmated Sandpiper	10	6.79	0.910	<0.001	*
Semipalmated Plover	12	7.36	Recorded in all counts	NS	
Spotted Sandpiper	9	7.43	0.894	<0.001	*
Collared Plover	11	8.19	0.879	<0.001	*
Short-billed Dowitcher	12	8.57	0.629	0.029	NS
Black-bellied Plover	12	8.86	0.670	0.017	NS
Willet	12	8.93	0.773	0.003	*
Southern Lapwing	12	9.02	0.601	0.039	NS
Ruddy Turnstone	12	9.09	0.640	0.025	NS
Least Sandpiper	11	9.56	0.733	0.007	NS
Sanderling	12	9.73	0.306	0.334	NS
Whimbrel	12	9.79	0.299	0.346	NS

Probably most were immatures.

No Greater or Lesser Yellowlegs were recorded in June but small numbers of both were seen in July. Possibly these were early returning adults.

No Hudsonian Godwits were recorded at Aracaju in June or July, but immatures of this species are known to spend the austral winter further south, e.g. in southern Chile (Espinosa *et al.* 2006). Similarly, although no Red Knots were seen at Aracaju in June or July, it is thought that all immatures of the Tierra del Fuego population remain in South America; however their whereabouts in the austral winter is unclear (Niles *et al.* 2007).

Collared Plovers and Southern Lapwings are year-round residents and common breeders during the austral spring along the Sergipe coast; however, neither are found commonly in mangroves.

The mangrove-lined coast of Sergipe, where shorebirds feed and rest, is also used by tourists for recreation, shrimp-farming and for the disposal of industrial and domestic waste. Human activities generate considerable disturbance to the shorebirds, especially when they are roosting over high tide, forcing them to fly from place to place and increasing their energy expenditure (Burger 1986). Such energy loss can be particularly detrimental to long distance migrants that are laying down resources for migration (Dunn *et al.* 1988). Since the mid 1980s, the sandy, ocean-beaches of Sergipe, both close to the study site and elsewhere along the coast, have undergone a rapid process of urbanization associated with tourism and other leisure activities (Barbieri & Pinna 2005). Not only has this resulted in loss of shorebird habitat but it has also brought more vehicular traffic and more people to the coast and both have been shown to be highly disruptive to the lives of waterbirds (Klein 1993, Klein *et al.* 1995). Together, these developments are altering the coast in a way that devalues extensive areas as shorebird habitat.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a need of more detailed studies to identify shorebird migratory routes along the Brazilian coast. It is also necessary and of fundamental importance to determine which areas are used by each species in order to protect them. This study shows that the Sergipe coast is one of the areas that need to be protected and managed to mitigate the effects of tourism, shrimp and shellfish farming activities and industrial waste. Human disturbance is a serious problem to migrant shorebirds, often displacing birds from prime foraging and roosting areas (Barbieri & Pinna 2005, Clark *et al.* 1993). An oil spill prior to or during migration might not only lead to mortality (Barbieri & Vooren 1993), but also deny access to food resources, and even cause migration to be suspended. The conservation of critical mangrove habitats in Sergipe State requires coast-wide coordination and management for long term protection of shorebirds. Issues to be addressed include oil-spill response planning, protection of shorebirds from disturbance, habitat acquisition and protection, and non-consumptive user management. This study aimed to establish base-line data to allow future comparisons and assess the impact of urbanization on the birds.

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APPENDIX

Weekly counts of shorebirds at Aracaju, Sergipe, Brazil, between January 2003 and April 2005 summarised by monthly mean (\pm SE) with pie-charts showing the proportion of weekly counts in each month that the species was recorded (the black segment).

(Appendix continued...)

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